

Brand image and personality of a sonified website.

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Abstract

Brand image, product- and brand- personality play an important role in the decision to buy a product. Websites are one of the media a brand may use to communicate its image and personality. In comparison with visual imagery, the use of sound as a carrier of brand-identity, and -personality in websites is hardly used and research in this field is very limited. However, it has been shown that sound or music has a positive influence in conveying a brand in advertising. In two experiments the role of sound in conveying a brand and product personality on a website was investigated. Three versions of a website (*no sound*, *sound congruent* with the website, *sound not congruent* with the website) were designed, while keeping the visual imagery equal. These sites were evaluated on their brand personality using a between subject design. In Experiment 1, the evoked brand personality of the websites was investigated using a brand personality scale (Govers, 2004). Although the influence of sound was not in the expected direction it was shown that the two sonifications of the website influenced the perceived personality in a positive and negative way in comparison with the non-sonified website. In Experiment 2, it was tested why the congruent sonification influenced the perceived personality in an opposite direction than we expected in Experiment 1. Suggestions for other sonifications are discussed.

Keywords: Brand personality, website, sonification.

The use of sound in marketing

Nowadays, quality is becoming less and less an added value. The so-called “hard factors” of a product –(technical quality, functional properties or costs/price relations)- are no longer by themselves enough for a company to distinguish itself from the competition. If the qualitative distinction between products or services decreases then the emotional value should increase (Franzen & Holzhauer, 1988). Factors like brand image and brand associations are emotional factors in a consumer’s decision to buy a product (Kapferer, 2001). Another important aspect in the preference for a brand of product is product personality (Govers, 2004). Many studies have shown that people prefer those brands (Aaker, 1997) and products (Jordan, 1997) that are consistent with their self-concept. The appearance of a product can be an important determinant of product personality (Govers, 2004). Product personality is not communicated only through a design, other forms of communication can play an important part.

A website is one of the media through which a brand communicates its image and personality. Traditionally, imagery, typography, and colors are the modalities or constituents to design a website. The structural use of sound in websites is relatively new, and, given that affective reactions to and evaluations of auditory stimuli are fundamental components of human perception (Västfjäll, Gubol, Kleiner & Gärling, 2002) it may present companies with new branding opportunities.

The focus of most research conducted on the effect of sound (often music) and brand image has been on the effect of background music on product choice and brand attitude, especially in commercials. Gorn (1982) conducted an experiment in which the subjects were shown different colored pens while music was being played in the background. The two pens were identical except for the color (both colors were rated neutral). The music had been previously rated as pleasant (common pop music) or unpleasant (classical Indian music) by other participants. The participants were offered a free choice of pens after the experiment was finished. It was found that 79% of the subjects in the pleasant music condition chose a pen of the same color they had seen while listening to the music.

Seventy percent of the participants in the unpleasant music condition chose a pen of a different color from the one they were shown while listening to the music. A replication of this study by Groenland and Schoormans (1994) yielded the same results. Middlestadt, Fishbein, and Chan (1993) conducted an experiment in which the participants were shown a television commercial for an (non-existing) applejuice brand, one group without background music and one group with background music. Data showed that the advertisement with background music evoked a subtle but significant positive impact on the perception of naturalness, clarity, freshness, thirst, quenching taste, and flavor towards that (non-existing) applejuice brand. Analysis suggested that this difference in attitude towards the brand was due to a change in underlying cognitive structure, rather than a purely affective change. Kellaris, Cox, and Cox (1993) showed that the effect of music in the perception of advertising can be explained as an interplay between attention-gaining value and a positive or negative music message congruency, in which both properties can enhance each other. Hung (2001) showed that in a teaser ad, music connects- and accentuates- with, selective visual events, as well as selective aspects of a visual event. In this way the maker of the teaser ad can frame the viewer through music, in a manner similar to verbal captions. In conclusion, sound and music have a large influence on brand image, brand attitude and product choice.

In conclusion, the knowledge described above is frequently and carefully applied in television, radio, and cinema advertisements. The use of sound in websites has—to our knowledge—not been elaborately studied. Can this knowledge be used in websites too? First, we should recognize that sound in websites has multi-purposes. It can be used to enhance brand image, strengthen connections between products and emotions, but it is also used to provide feedback on user-interaction.

Sonification in websites

The user of a website must be stimulated to search for information in or at a specific place. This can be achieved in sonification by using the signal functions a sound can possess (Kunst, 1978; den Otter, van Egmond 2005), by playing with the context of a sound in a website, or by manipulating the parameters (e.g. loudness, pitch, spatiality) of a sound. The perception of sound yields features that can be used to the benefit of

the interaction design. For example, no one can see a car approaching around the corner of a house, but you can hear it. There is also the ability to perceive and locate something 360 degrees around. In comparison, our field of vision is limited to approximately 150 degrees (in film and multimedia terms one would say off-screen). This advantage could be exploited much more when designing an interface, not only for websites, but also for a whole range of interfaces in general. If this is understood, and the right balance of hedonics and ergonomics (Hassenzahl, 2000) is applied, sound can be used to enhance certain aspects or even to open up a new range of possibilities (den Otter & van Egmond, 2005). However, if sound or music is not applied in the proper manner (often caused because of a lack of knowledge of sound) it may get annoying and people switch off the sound of their computer.

Previous experiments showed us that the timbre of a sound could communicate many “associations” (descriptions that carry the exact personality characteristics of the company or brand that they portray) to a listener (Kapferer, 2001). If this is combined with the inherent emotional impact of music and sound (think of the sound from a thunderstorm), the impact of branding through sonification of a website may be very powerful. In the next experiment we investigate if and how sonification could contribute to the perception of a brand and of a product personality on a website. Three versions of a website (“no-sound, sound congruent with the website, sound not congruent with the website) were designed, while keeping the visual imagery unaltered. These sites were evaluated on their brand personality.

Experiment 1

Method

Three versions (no sound, congruent sound, incongruent sound) of the Max Factor website were evaluated using product personality attributes from Govers (2004) in a between-subject design

Participants

Forty-five undergraduate students and employees of the Delft University of Technology volunteered in the experiment. The participants were all female, as the Max Factor brand targets their products specifically on females. The oldest was 26

years, the youngest 18 years ($M=22$).

Stimuli

The Max factor website in Dutch was chosen. This site was on-line in March 2005. The website contained a homepage and seven subpages. The subpages were called: “teint” (complexion), “ogen” (eyes), “lippen” (lips), “nagels” (nails), “visagisten studio” (visagists studio), ”max factor club”, and “over max factor” (about max factor). In Figure 1, a screenshot of the Max Factor homepage is shown. This website was chosen because Max Factor selected the depicted models to fit its brand image. The models should therefore reflect the personality image of the brand.

Figure 1. Screenshot of the Max Factor homepage, used in Experiment 1.

Design

We used the original website without sound in the No-sound condition. Next, two additional versions of the website were designed. One version was sonified with a soundscape thought to be congruent with the visual imagery of the Max Factor brand image, another version was sonified with a soundscape designed to be incongruent with the brand image of Max Factor. The latter sonification was designed to be

compliant with the so-called “Gothic Style”

[http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gothic_fashion], hereafter called “Incongruent”. This style was chosen, because it represented to us the (visual) opposite of the Max Factor, but the use of make-up remains an important styling factor.

Table 1. Experiential properties of sounds that were used to design the soundscapes of the websites.

Max Factor (Congruent)	Overlapping	Goth (Incongruent)
Irratic	Polished	Controlled
Diverse	Mysterious	Monotone
Noisy	Divined	Common
Spacious		Beat
		Dark
		Enclosed

After a workshop with students at the TU-Delft, we used experiential properties of the Max Factor brand and the Gothic lifestyle for the sonification of the websites, as can be seen in Table 1. Some of the experiential properties of Max Factor and Gothic lifestyle overlapped. Two sonifications were designed on the basis of the experiential properties shown in Table 1. The Congruent sonification consisted of sounds and soundloops of shopping malls, car horns, a party, ice-cubes, catwalk, and photographer sounds. The Incongruent sonification consisted of sounds and soundloops of low-pitched electronic sounds, low-pitched drones, sounds of scratched glass, and chorus like sounds.

Procedure

Three groups of 15 participants were shown a website of the Max Factor cosmetics, in either a No sound, Congruent, and Incongruent condition. The sonified websites could be heard through headphones. Participants were given a few minutes to browse through the different parts of the website in order to become acquainted with the atmosphere of the website. They were asked to complete three visual search tasks on the website to ensure that they properly experienced the website. When a participant indicated that she had seen enough of the website, she could call the interviewer for the next stage of the experiment. Participants were then asked to rate the website (on a scale of one to nine) on 20 personality descriptions stemming from Govers (2004).

Descriptions were presented in Dutch and were:

Aloof (Afstandelijk), Boring (Saai), Obtrusive (Opdringerig), Untidy (Slordig), Silly (Dom), Dominant (Dominant), Pretty (Leuk), Easy Going (Vlot), Relaxed (Relaxed), Cheerful (Vrolijk), Open (Open), Idiosyncratic (Eigenzinnig), Interesting (Interessant), Provocative (Uitdagend), Lively (Pittig), Honest (Eerlijk), Modest (Bescheiden), Serious (Serieus), Cute (Schattig) and Childish (Kinderachtig).

Results

To simplify the comparison of the results for the 3 conditions, we decided to first factor analyse the ratings on the 20 personality descriptions, using a Principle Component extraction with Varimax rotation. It involves rotating the axes in the space created by the factors to help identify variables that load on the same factor. Based on the scree-plot criterion and the Eigen-values greater than 1, we chose a five factor solution. In Table 2 the Factor loadings and the Intra-class correlation coefficients of the attributes are presented. The intra-class correlations were calculated to determine the agreement of the participants on their judgments of the three sites. The explained variance of each factor is given at the bottom of the table. The following factors were identified; “Forthright Personality factors” (Fact 1), “Comfortable Personality factors” (Fact 2), “Daring Personality factors” (Fact 3) “Sincere Personality factors” (Fact 4), and “Immature Personality factors” (Fact 5). As can be seen the explained variance for the factors was relatively low. In addition, the intra-class correlation coefficients for most of the attributes were rather low.

Table 2. Factor loadings of personality attributes extracted with PCA and Varimax rotation. ICC is the intra-class correlation (model: two-way random, absolute agreement) for an attribute.

	<i>Fact 1</i>	<i>Fact2</i>	<i>Fact3</i>	<i>Fact4</i>	<i>Fact5</i>	<i>ICC</i>
Aloof (Afstandelijk)	.780	-.132	.052	.174	-.146	-.015
Boring (Saai)	.701	-.136	-.312	-.023	-.188	-.010
Obtrusive (Opdringerig)	.626	-.065	.347	-.422	-.021	.022
Untidy (Slordig)	.585	.014	-.206	.267	.097	-.050
Silly (Dom)	.547	-.291	-.053	-.118	.285	.083
Dominant (Dominant)	.490	.482	-.028	-.463	.143	0.34
Pretty (Leuk)	-.315	.709	.099	.008	-.058	-.035
Easy Going (Vlot)	-.299	.671	.209	.034	.177	-.071
Relaxed (Relaxed)	.219	.622	.007	.180	.071	-.057
Cheerful (Vrolijk)	-.176	.567	.132	-.159	-.169	.160
Open (Open)	-.027	.509	.037	.391	.171	-.060
Idiosyncratic (Eigenzinnig)	.088	.292	.813	-.083	.133	-.071
Interesting (Interessant)	-.148	.102	.763	.243	-.026	.019
Provocative (Uitdagend)	-.092	-.086	.722	-.095	-.134	-.023
Lively (Pittig)	-.128	.388	.615	-.012	-.284	-.040
Honest (Eerlijk)	.036	.223	-.019	.860	-.057	-.069
Modest (Bescheiden)	-.038	.023	-.101	.802	.146	-.063
Serious (Serieus)	.254	-.133	.292	.576	-.037	.055
Cute (Schattig)	-.173	-.005	-.043	.124	.830	-.041
Childisch (Kinderachtig)	.098	.083	-.093	-.034	.799	.002
% of variance	19.213	13.262	11.687	9.830	7.301	

In order to gain insight how the websites are positioned on the different factors, two figures were created. In Figures 2 and 3 the different website conditions are depicted in a space spanned up by Factors 1 and 2, and Factors 3 and 4, respectively. Note in the graphical representation the factors are scaled.

Figure 2. The three website conditions positioned on the “Forthright Personality factor” (Fact 1, X-axis) and “Comfortable Personality factor” (Fact 2, Y-axis).

In Figure 2 the “Comfortable Personality factor” is shown as a function of the “Forthright Personality factor”. As can be seen the Incongruent and Congruent conditions are represented relatively high on the “Forthright Personality factor”. The Incongruent condition is represented relatively high on the Comfortable Personality factor, whereas the Congruent condition is represented relatively low on this factor. The No sound condition is represented relatively low on the “Comfortable Personality factor” and rated close to zero on the “Forthright Personality factor”.

Figure 3. The three website conditions positioned on the “Daring Personality factor” (Fact 3, Y-axis) and “Sincere Personality factor” (Fact 4, X-axis).

In Figure 3, the positioning of the website conditions in the space spanned up by the “Daring Personality factor” and the “Sincere Personality factor” are shown. As can be seen the Congruent website is positioned relatively high on the Daring personality factor, whereas the Incongruent and the No sound conditions are positioned relatively low. However, the Congruent condition is positioned low on the “Sincere Personality factor”, whereas the NoSound and Incongruent conditions are positioned relatively high on this factor.

The positioning on the non-depicted Factor 5, “Childish personality factor” did not show a large differentiation. The Congruent condition was slightly higher than the No-sound condition that was close to zero. The Incongruent condition was just below zero.

Discussion

A difference in the perceived “personality” between the three conditions was expected. We hypothesized that the “Congruent” condition would match the brand values of Max Factor more than the “Incongruent” condition. In the case of the “Daring personality factor”, this is true. However, the “Forthright personality factor” was represented higher in the “Congruent” condition than in the “Incongruent” condition. This may have different reasons. Almost all participants indicated that they knew the brand Max Factor, but only a few of them actually used make-up products produced by Max Factor. It could be that the attitude towards Max Factor with the students already was Incongruent. This is something that needs to be considered for a future experiment. Another reason may be that participants actually did not like that sounds were added to the site. In addition, the experimental setting and the use of a headphone may also have been of influence. Soundscapes are designed to function somewhat in the background, a presentation through a headphone may yield a relatively high attention focus to the sound. Participants also indicated that the “car” and “car-horn” sounds in the Congruent condition were annoying to them. The drone-like and slow sounds in the “Incongruent” condition could have contributed to the perception of a relaxed personality than the more hectic and cosmopolitan “Congruent” condition.

Hevner reported on this phenomenon (1937). She demonstrated the relationship

between tempo and mode and happiness versus sadness judgments, stating that tempo was the most important factor. Music with a slow tempo that was played in a minor tone-scale was perceived in the Thoughtfully and Sensitive emotion group, and music played with a slow tempo and a simple harmony was perceived in the Serene and Tender emotion group. In the Incongruent condition there are spots in which the harmony is simple and throughout the whole condition the sounds and loops move at a slow pace. In any case, this experiment shows that the sonified websites do contribute to the perception of the personality of a website more than a non-sonified website does. In the personality factors, except the “Forthright personality factor” the No-sound condition was associated with the value zero, whereas the Congruent and Incongruent conditions always showed a result other than zero. Thus, indicating that the unsonified website is perceived with a “neutral” personality.

The low explained variance and ICC coefficients may be explained by the complexity of the task. In addition, the between-subject design may also have caused these low values. ICC coefficients are mostly calculated over different conditions but using the same judges. The between-subject design causes different judges to rate each condition. This may yield in less agreement and thus a lower ICC. A within-subject design may have been a better choice because the participants would have received each condition. This design may enhance the differentiation between the websites and thus yield better results. In addition, the increase in the number of subjects in a between subjects design may also yield better results. These experimental design issues will be addressed in future research.

The findings of the experiment also indicate the interaction of sound and the visual imagery of a website is more complex than was expected. In order to understand why results in the Congruent condition differed from what we expected, we conducted a second experiment in which the congruent sound version was tested on its fit with the website.

Experiment 2

Method

The congruent website was tested on how well it fitted to the Mac Factor brand and to the Max Factor website.

Participants

Ten undergraduate students of the Delft University of Technology volunteered in the experiment. The participants were all female.

Stimuli

The Max factor website in Dutch was chosen. This site was on-line in March 2005. It was the same website as was used in Experiment 1.

Design

The soundscape of the congruent condition was changed a little based on the comments obtained by participants of Experiment 1. The city and street life sounds were made more clearly audible in this condition, because these received the most comments. The “car” and “car horn” sounds remained in the soundscape because they are important to evoke a metropolitan experience with the soundscape.

Procedure

The participants received the same instructions as in Experiment 1 to familiarize themselves with the website. The congruent soundscapes was then played and participants were asked to give their opinion (on a scale of one to nine, one representing do not agree at all, nine representing totally agree) on the following five statements.

1. I think Max Factor and this sound complete each other.
2. I think the sound adds something to the brand.
3. I think this is a suitable ambient sound for the Max Factor website.
4. I think Max Factor suits this sound
5. I think this sound and the Max Factor website are similar

Results

Figure 4. Mean ratings to the 5 statements asked to rate how well the sound fitted to the brand (statements 1, 2, and 4) and to the site (statements 3 and 5). Error bars represent the Standard Error of the Mean.

As can be seen in Figure 4, the general ratings are not that high. None of the individual subjects rated the statements above a seven. The ratings to statements 1, 2 and 4 (sound fit to brand) were higher than for the ratings to statements 3 and 5 (sound fit to website). Questions 1 and 2 were rated above the average of 4.5. The rating values were analyzed with an ANOVA. A significant effect of Question was found, $F(4, 36)=7.29$, $p<.001$. A post-hoc analysis revealed significant effects between questions 1-3, 1-5, 2-3, 2-5, 3-4, and 4-5.

General Discussion

The main finding of Experiment 2 is that the suggested soundscape was compatible with the Max Factor brand and not with the Max Factor website. After the interviews

some of the subjects indicated that most of them thought the noisy, city-life sounds in the soundscape matches the brand-image though they missed a glamorous aspect. The website however, differed in this respect. Visually, the website appeared serene and smooth, perhaps not corresponding to the more metropolitan brand image of Max Factor. This might suggest that the brand image and the visual imagery of the website are not congruent. However, we should be careful to speculate on this because we have not tested how well the site fitted the brand image. In our future research this will be tested more extensively. It would be interesting to investigate the difference between a metropolitan and glamorous sonification of the website, more congruent with the brand image of Max Factor, and a more serene and inward looking soundscape that is more congruent with the visual communication of the website itself.

There is also an indication that the pace of the sounds and tempo of the soundloops have influence on the perception of the website. This is in accordance with findings in music psychology (Hevner, 1937). The systematic variation of these factors is an additional aspect we want to consider in our future research. But most important, it can be suggested that a sonified website contributes more to the perception of a personality of a website than a non-sonified website.

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References

Aaker, J. (1997) "Dimensions of Brand Personality". *Journal of Marketing Research*, 34, 347-357.

Franzen, G. And Holzhauer F. (1988) *Het Merk*. (The Brand) Zutphen: Kluwer.

Gorn, G. J. (1982) "The Effects of Music in Advertising on Choice Behavior: A Classical Conditioning Approach". *Journal of Marketing*, 46, 94-101.

Govers, P.C.M. (2004) *Product Personality*. (Phd-thesis). Delft: Delft University of Technology.

Groenland, E. A. G. And Schoormans, J. P. L. (1994) "Comparing Mood-Induction and Affective Conditioning as Mechanisms Influencing Product Evaluation and Product Choice". *Psychology and Marketing*, 11, 183-197.

Hassenzahl, And M. Platz, And A. Burmester, M. And Lehner, K. (2000) "Hedonic and ergonomic quality aspects determine a software's appeal". In Turner, T. Szwillus, G. Czerwinski, M. Peterno, F. Pemberton, S. (eds) *Proceedings of the CHI 2000 Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (pp. 201–208). New York: ACM, Addison-Wesley.

Hevner, K. (1937) "The affective value of pitch and tempo in music." *American Journal of Psychology*, 49, 621-630.

Hung, K. (2001), "Framing Meaning Perceptions with Music: the Case of Teaser Ads." *Journal of Advertising*, 2001, 30 (Fall), 39-50.

Jordan, P.W. (1997) "Products as personalities". In Robertson, S. A. (Ed.) *Contemporary Ergonomics 1997*. London: Taylor & Francis, pp. 73-78.

Kapferer, J-N (2001) *(Re)inventing the brand*. London: Kogan Page Limited.

Kellaris, J.J. And Cox A.D. And Cox D. (1993) The effect of background music on ad processing: a contingency explanation. *Journal of Marketing*, 57, 114-25.

Kunst, J. (1978) *Making sense in music: an enquiry into the formal pragmatics of art*. Gent: Communication & cognition.

Middlestadt, S.E. And Fishbein, M. And Chan, D.K. (1994) “The effect of music on brand attitudes: affect or belief-based change?” In E. Clark, T. and Brock and D. Stewart (Eds.), *Attention, attitude, and affect in response to advertising* (pp.149-167). Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum.

Otter, R den. And Egmond, R van. (2005) Possibilities for sonification in webdesign. In Wensveen, S. Diederiks, E. Djajadiningrat, T. Guenand, A. Klooster, S. Stienstra, M. Vink, P. and, Overbeeke, K. (Eds.) *Proceedings of the conference designing pleasurable products and interfaces* (pp. 283-292). Eindhoven: Technische Universiteit

Västfjäll, D. And Gulbol, M-A. And Kleiner, M. And Gärling, T. (2002) “Affective reactions to- and evaluations of interior and exterior vehicle auditory quality”. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, 255, 501-518.